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“IS LIFE GREEN”

Life is shrouded in colors of green,
Where old wounds heal and new dreams sheen.
Time breathes slow in this whimsical dream,
Where nothing is quite as clear as it seems.

Green is yellow when rays are near;
The wind speaks of secrets no one hears.
Tears pour in puddles of ten,
Where shadows of Zen waltz again.

Come the day where life is dead—
Yellow has flit, one left by a thread.
The world is stripped, bare at its branch,
Banished for good—clouds bowed to crack.

Life is never just green;
It's yellow, brown, and spirit—the perfect in-between.
The earth's belly rumbles in hum,
A telltale symbol of what's yet to become.